

Values Education Practices and the Implementation of Child Protection Measures in Public Schools

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Abstract. This study examined the relationship between values education practices and the extent of implementation of child protection measures in public schools in Tugbok East District Davao City. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, data were gathered from teachers through a validated survey instrument measuring the integration of core values in instruction and child protection implementation. Results revealed that values, education practices, and child protection measures were implemented at a moderately extensive level. A strong and significant positive relationship was found between values education practices and the implementation of child protection measures. Regression analysis further showed that values-oriented school activities significantly influenced child protection implementation. At the same time, integration of core values in instruction and teacher modeling was not a significant predictor when analyzed concurrently. The findings suggested that school-wide and participatory values initiatives play a crucial role in strengthening child protection systems. The study concluded that fostering a values-based school culture is essential in promoting safe, respectful, and learner-centered environments. The study recommended strengthening school-wide values programs, enhancing stakeholder engagement, and providing continuous professional development to ensure effective and sustainable child protection practices in public schools.

KEY WORDS

1. child protection
2. values education practices
3. implementation of child protection measures

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1. Introduction

This study investigates how public schools implement values education alongside strategies to protect children's welfare. Public schools are responsible for nurturing students' values and ensuring their safety through effective protective measures. Integrating values education with child protection initiatives helps create a secure and respectful school culture. Likewise, values education and child protection initiatives encounter numerous challenges rooted in both

the school system and society. These challenges include inconsistent integration of core values across subjects, varying teachers' abilities to model ethical behavior, and limited stakeholder involvement in promoting relevant policies.

Additionally, Casipe and Bete (2023) highlighted that context-sensitive approaches, such as psychosocial support and team-based learning, strengthen child protection initiatives. These concerns underscore the need for this

study, which aimed to provide evidence to enhance educational practices and policies. Given the impact of values education on child protection, this research contributes to social value by offering insights that support the creation of safer, more nurturing, and ethically sound learning environments for Filipino students.

Worldwide, many countries have struggled to implement values education and child protection in schools (The Times, 2025). The UK government faced criticism after shifting from comprehensive, judge-led inquiries into grooming gangs to letting local councils decide how to use allocated funds, resulting in smaller initiatives and concerns about insufficient action. This change has raised questions about the effectiveness and timeliness of child protection efforts. The IFRC has urged immediate steps to shield children from violence, especially during crises and disasters (IFRC, 2024). Their 2025–2028 Appeal calls for collaboration with schools and communities to create safer learning spaces and prevent violence through education. This initiative illustrates the persistent difficulties in protecting children’s rights during worldwide crises.

Moreover, as reported by Le Monde (2024), concerns have been raised in France about the potential regression of children’s rights following recent political developments. The President of UNICEF France expressed alarm over the absence of childhood issues in political debates, except for announcements of tougher penal policies treating minors as adults. Such shifts risk exacerbating inequalities and compromising children’s futures, highlighting the need for comprehensive national strategies to support children’s rights across the country.

In the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), ongoing socio-political tensions had significantly hindered the implementation of child protection measures. Efforts to disengage children from armed groups, such as the Moro Islamic Liberation

Front (MILF), have been notable; however, reintegrating these children into society remains a complex issue. The United Nations reported that nearly 2,000 children were disengaged from MILF ranks, highlighting the need for comprehensive support systems to facilitate their return to civilian life and prevent re-recruitment (United Nations Office of the Special Representative of the Secretary-General for Children and Armed Conflict, 2021). This underscores the necessity for sustainable educational and psychosocial programs tailored to the unique context of BARMM.

Also, in the NCR, limited access to devices and the internet has deepened educational inequalities, with over 40% of students lacking the necessary tools for online learning (Beech, 2021). Many depend on self-learning modules instead. This digital divide hinders effective values education by restricting meaningful interaction and engagement.

Furthermore, in the Tugbok East District, schools such as Mintal, Tacunan, Matina Biao, Tugbok Central, and Biao Elementary have continued to serve students, but in the wider Davao Region, the closure of around 200 Lumad schools due to alleged insurgent links has disrupted education for about 10,000 Indigenous children (Wikipedia contributors, 2024). This has raised serious concerns about access to education and the protection of Indigenous cultural identity. The situation highlights the urgent need for policies that ensure inclusive, culturally sensitive education for all learners.

Further, promoting values education alongside child protection in public schools is vital for fostering a safe and respectful environment where all students can thrive. These efforts support the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal for quality education by ensuring every child has equal access to learning that builds both knowledge and character. To effectively spread these practices, it is important to train teachers, involve the wider community, and use

various platforms for awareness, ensuring consistent and meaningful application in everyday school life.

However, by acknowledging the challenges faced by values education and child protection initiatives in schools and society, this statement highlights areas requiring attention and improvement. Its social value lies in raising awareness

about these critical issues, prompting stakeholders to take action towards creating safer, more ethical, and supportive environments for children. Ultimately, such recognition fosters collective responsibility and advocacy for reforms that promote the well-being and holistic development of students.

2. Methodology

This chapter outlined the research methodology employed in the study, including the selection of respondents, research instruments, data gathering procedures, sampling technique, statistical treatment, and ethical considerations. The nature of the inquiry and the insights sought guided the choice of research design and its implementation, which are discussed in the sections that follow.

Research Design— This study used a descriptive-correlational and predictive research design to examine the relationship between values education practices and the implementation of child protection measures in public schools. The design was appropriate because the study described existing practices and tested whether variations in values education practices were significantly associated with, and predictive of, child protection implementation. Quantitative data were gathered through a structured survey and analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression procedures.

Respondents— The respondents were public elementary school teachers from five selected schools in Tugbok East District, Davao City, namely Mintal, Tacunan, Matina Biao, Tugbok Central, and Biao Elementary School. From a population of 180 teachers, Slovin's formula was used to determine a sample of 124 teacher-respondents. The respondents were selected because of their direct participation in classroom instruction, values education activities, and school-based child protection practices.

Research Instruments— The survey instrument measured two constructs: values education practices and the implementation of child protection measures. Values education practices cov-

ered integration of core values in instruction, teacher modeling and reinforcement, and values-oriented school activities. Child protection implementation covered reporting and management of child protection incidents, stakeholders' awareness and participation, and preventive and responsive mechanisms. The questionnaire used a five-point Likert scale. Reliability testing yielded acceptable internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha values of 0.8213 for values education practices and 0.8367 for child protection implementation.

Data Gathering Procedure— The researcher secured the necessary approvals from the adviser, the Graduate School, and DepEd authorities before data collection. After permission was granted, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the respondents, explained the purpose of the study, and ensured voluntary participation. Completed questionnaires were retrieved, checked for completeness, coded, and prepared for statistical analysis.

Sampling Technique— Stratified random sampling was used to ensure fair representation from the participating schools. The teacher population from each school was considered in selecting the respondents so that the final sample reflected the distribution of teachers across the

selected schools in Tugbok East District. *Statistical Treatment*— The data were encoded, checked, and analyzed using statistical software. Mean and standard deviation were used to describe the extent of values education practices and child protection implementation. Pearson correlation was used to determine the significance and strength of the relationship between the variables. Multiple linear regression was used to determine which domain of values education practices significantly influenced the

implementation of child protection measures. *Ethical Considerations*— The study followed ethical standards on informed consent, voluntary participation, privacy, confidentiality, and responsible data handling. Respondents were informed of the purpose of the study and their right to decline or withdraw without penalty. Data were coded and reported in aggregate form to protect participants' identities. The researcher also observed fairness, transparency, and respect throughout the conduct of the study.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the summarized results and discussion of the study on values education practices and the implementation of child protection measures in public schools. Only the summary tables, significant relationship table, and regression analysis table are retained to emphasize the major statistical findings and their implications.

Summary of Values Education Practices— The summary of values education practices shows that the three domains were generally implemented at a moderately extensive level. Integration of core values in instruction, teacher mod-

eling and reinforcement, and values-oriented school activities were evident in the schools, although the overall mean suggests that these practices still require stronger consistency and more systematic school-wide implementation.

Table 1
Summary of the Extent of Values Education Practices

Indicator	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Integration of core values in instruction	3.23	.276	Moderately Extensive
Teacher modeling and reinforcement	3.24	.301	Moderately Extensive
Values-oriented school activity	3.18	.286	Moderately Extensive
Mean Average	3.22	.268	Moderately Extensive

The result indicates that values education was present in classroom instruction and school activities but was not yet fully institutionalized across all areas. This implies that public schools may strengthen deliberate integration of DepEd core values in lesson delivery, teacher modeling, classroom routines, and co-curricular programs. *Summary of Child Protection Measures*— The summary of child protection implementation

shows that reporting and management of incidents, stakeholders' awareness and participation, and preventive and responsive mechanisms were rated moderately extensive. This suggests that child protection structures and activities were practiced but still need sustained monitoring, stronger stakeholder engagement, and more consistent implementation.

Table 2
Summary of the Extent of Implementation of Child Protection Measures

Indicator	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
Reporting and management of child protection incidents	3.17	.359	Moderately Extensive
Stakeholders' awareness and participation	3.39	.295	Moderately Extensive
Preventive and responsive mechanisms	3.16	.334	Moderately Extensive
Mean Average	3.24	.225	Moderately Extensive

The findings suggest that child protection systems in the schools were functional but still developing. Strengthening reporting procedures, school-based awareness campaigns, Child Protection Committee activities, and referral mechanisms may help improve the consistency and responsiveness of child protection implementation.

Significant Relationship— The correlation result shows a strong and significant positive relationship between values education practices and the implementation of child protection measures. This means that stronger values education practices tend to be associated with stronger child protection implementation.

Table 3
Relationship Between Values Education Practices and the Implementation of Child Protection Measures

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Values Education Practices and Implementation of Child Protection Measures	0.713	< .001	Significant	Reject H0

Note. Significant at $p < .05$.

The significant relationship supports the view that a values-based school culture contributes to safe, respectful, and learner-centered environments. When schools consistently promote respect, responsibility, empathy, and discipline, child protection policies become more meaningful and easier to practice.

identifies which values education domain significantly predicts the implementation of child protection measures. The findings show that values-oriented school activities had the strongest predictive influence, while integration of core values in instruction and teacher modeling were not significant predictors when analyzed together.

Regression Analysis— The regression analysis

Table 4
Regression Analysis of Values Education Practices on the Implementation of Child Protection Measures

Model	Predictor	B	SE	β	t
M0	Intercept	3.241	0.020	–	160.661
M1	Intercept	1.355	0.166	–	8.142
	Integration of core values	0.078	0.083	0.096	0.938
	Teacher modeling and reinforcement	-0.099	0.098	-0.133	-1.009
	Values-oriented school activity	0.614	0.116	0.783	5.281

The regression result implies that school-wide and participatory values activities are especially important in strengthening child protection implementation. These activities make values visible through shared routines, cam-

paigns, programs, and learner participation. Thus, schools may prioritize values-oriented activities that are explicitly connected with child safety, respectful behavior, anti-bullying initiatives, and responsible stakeholder participation.

4. Summary of Findings, Conclusions, and Recommendations

This section presents the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations of the study. The discussion is presented in full-width form for the introductory statement, while the succeeding subsections provide the concise synthesis of the major findings and the corresponding implications for school practice.

Summary of Findings— The study found that values education practices in public schools were implemented at a moderately extensive level. Integration of core values in instruction, teacher modeling and reinforcement, and values-oriented school activities were evident, although the findings indicate that these practices still require stronger consistency and school-wide alignment. The implementation of child protection measures was also rated moderately extensive, showing that reporting mechanisms, stakeholder awareness, and preventive and responsive mechanisms were present but not yet fully optimized. The relationship analysis revealed a strong and significant positive association between values education practices and the implementation of child protection measures. Regression results further showed that values-oriented school activities significantly influenced the implementation of child protection measures, while integration of core values in instruction and teacher modeling were not significant predictors when analyzed together.

Conclusions— Based on the findings, the study concludes that values education practices are meaningfully associated with the implementation of child protection measures in public schools. A values-based school culture helps strengthen learner protection by promoting respect, responsibility, empathy, discipline, and stakeholder participation. The findings further suggest that school-wide and participatory values-oriented activities serve as an important pathway for strengthening child protection implementation because these activities translate values into shared routines and visible school practices.

Recommendations— Schools may strengthen values education by making core values more explicit in classroom instruction, homeroom activities, school programs, and learner support initiatives. Teachers may continue to model respectful, ethical, and child-friendly behavior while reinforcing positive conduct through consistent feedback and classroom routines. School heads may institutionalize school-wide values-oriented activities that are directly linked with child protection goals. The Child Protection Committee may conduct regular orientation, reporting drills, monitoring, and stakeholder engagement activities to improve policy awareness and responsiveness. Future researchers may examine the same variables in other districts or include learner, parent, and school-head perspectives to obtain a broader view of values education and child protection implementation.

5. References

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